

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ADOPTION BY ENTERPRISES IN SERBIA

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Abstract: *This paper analyzes the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies among enterprises in Serbia, with a comparative view of their position relative to companies in the European Union. The research is based on desk analysis of secondary data sourced from Eurostat. Although the overall number of enterprises using AI in Serbia remains relatively low, it is steadily growing. Large enterprises are the most active adopters, with the Information and Communication sector leading in implementation. The most commonly used AI technologies include text analysis (text mining) and machine learning methods such as deep learning for data processing. AI is predominantly applied in areas such as marketing and sales, as well as research, development, and innovation.*

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, SMEs, Serbia, EU.*

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are increasingly reshaping the business landscape by enhancing automation, improving decision-making, and enabling new forms of value creation. While large enterprises often lead in adoption due to greater resource availability, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are beginning to explore AI as a tool for improving productivity, efficiency, and innovation potential.

AI is recognized as a key enabler of digital transformation, yet its implementation often requires enterprises to undergo substantial technical and organizational changes ranging from adjusting data formats to overhauling entire business processes or roles, with many companies struggling due to complex data and process requirements (Rittelmeyer &

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Sandkuhl, 2021). Cui, Xu, and Razzaq (2022) demonstrate that artificial intelligence plays a meaningful role in enhancing corporate governance by increasing information symmetry and supporting more effective managerial decision-making. Davenport et al. (2020) argue that AI enhances business performance by boosting revenue through improved marketing and reducing costs via automation of routine tasks and services. Brynjolfsson et al. (2021) argue that the paradox between rapid advances in AI and sluggish productivity growth is largely due to implementation lags, as the full benefits of AI dependent on complementary innovations, organizational change, and new skills have yet to be realized or adequately captured by traditional economic metrics.

Recent studies indicate that the adoption of AI in SMEs is frequently hindered by limited internal expertise, financial constraints, and concerns over data security, despite its significant potential to enhance marketing, customer relationship management, and decision-making processes (Okrczesik & Duda, 2024). McElheran et al. (2024) highlight that although AI adoption in production varies by industry, it is present across all sectors and is most common among dynamic young firms led by highly educated, experienced owners motivated by innovation or community impact.

The extent of AI adoption differs significantly across countries, reflecting variations in digital maturity, institutional support, and enterprise capabilities. Although AI deployment in EU member states has been subject to growing academic and policy interest, there is still limited evidence on how countries outside the EU, such as Serbia, are adopting to this technological shift.

In the Serbian context, several studies have pointed to both opportunities and constraints in implementing advanced digital technologies. Trbovich et al. (2020) note that despite progress in digital policy, Serbia faces major challenges in adopting Industry 4.0 technologies like AI, highlighting the need for stronger institutional support and research to advance broader digital transformation. According to Bulatović (2024), Serbia ranks 57th out of 193 countries in the 2023 AI Readiness Index, demonstrating strong performance in AI-related regulation and ethics, along with moderately favorable infrastructure and data conditions. These indicators suggest that Serbia has a solid basis for advancing AI development, particularly through industry-specific innovation clusters and enhanced collaboration between government, businesses, and academia.

This paper aims to fill part of that gap by analyzing the current state of AI adoption among enterprises in Serbia and comparing it with patterns observed in the European Union. Special attention is paid to adoption differences by company size and sector, as well as to the specific purposes and types of AI technologies used. The paper contributes to understanding both the opportunities and the structural challenges that may hinder more widespread uptake.

The analysis is based on desk research utilizing secondary data from Eurostat, enabling a comparative, evidence-based assessment. This method provides a relevant snapshot of AI diffusion as of 2024 and highlights areas where targeted policy interventions and strategic investments could enhance Serbia's digital competitiveness.

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2. Results

In Serbia, 6.9% of enterprises used AI in their business activities in 2024, representing an increase of 6.05 percentage points compared to 2021 (Figure 1). In the same year, the EU recorded a share of enterprises using AI technologies nearly twice as high as in Serbia, reflecting a 5.83 percentage point increase from 2021.

Figure 1. Enterprises using AI technologies (% of enterprises), 2021/2024

Source: Eurostat (2024).

As shown in Figure 2, large enterprises lead in the adoption of AI technologies. In Serbia, 13.93% of large, 9.55% of medium, and 5.91% of small enterprises used AI technologies. The trends are similar in the EU, although the share of enterprises by size is more pronounced, with greater differences in the shares of firms of different sizes. The adoption of AI technologies is highest among large enterprises, with their share being almost three times higher than in Serbia. The next largest users are medium-sized enterprises (20.97%), while the share of small enterprises is the lowest at 11.21%.

Figure 2. Enterprises using AI technologies by size class (% of enterprises), 2024

Source: Eurostat (2024).

In some industries, AI technologies are more widely applied than in others (Figure 3). The information and communication and professional, scientific and technical activities industries have the highest adoption of AI technologies, both in Serbia and the EU. Nearly

half of the AI-using enterprises in the EU (48.72%) and a third of those in Serbia (28.81%) come from the information and communication sector. Every third EU enterprise (30.53%) and one in ten Serbian enterprises (11.71%) using AI come from the professional, scientific and technical activities sector. In all other sectors at the EU level, the share of enterprises using AI is less than 16%, with shares ranging from 15.45% (real estate activities) to 6.09% (construction), while in Serbia it ranges from 9.49% (transportation and storage) to 0% (real estate activities).

Figure 3. Enterprises using AI technologies by economic activity (% of enterprises), 2024

Note: C - Manufacturing; D_E - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply; water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities; F - Construction; G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; G47 - Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles; H - Transportation and storage; I55 -Accommodation; J - Information and communication; L68 - Real estate activities; M - Professional, scientific and technical activities; N - Administrative and support service activities.

Source: Eurostat (2024).

Enterprises used different types of AI technologies in their business activities. However, in both the EU and Serbia, no specific type of AI stood out significantly compared to others (Figure 4). What is similar between EU and Serbian enterprises is the type of AI technologies that were most and least commonly used. Around 6.88% of enterprises in the EU used AI technologies that enable text mining, while the share of such enterprises in Serbia was 3.98%. On the other hand, the least commonly used were autonomous robots, self-driving vehicles, and autonomous drones (EU – 1.01%; Serbia – 0.29%), as well as image recognition and image processing (EU – 3.23%; Serbia – 1.16%). Regarding other types of AI technologies, in Serbia, 3% of enterprises were used machine learning for data analysis, while between 1.99% and 1.51% enterprises were used technologies like AI-based software robotic process automation, speech recognition, natural language generation. The order in the EU is somewhat different. Natural language

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generation was used by 5.41% of enterprises, while speech recognition, machine learning for data analysis, and AI-based software robotic process automation were used by between 4.78% and 4.19% of enterprises.

Figure 4. Enterprises using AI technologies by type of AI technology (% of enterprises), 2024

Source: Eurostat (2024).

When observing the types of AI technologies used by enterprises of different sizes in Serbia, it is interesting to note that text mining is the technology most commonly used among small and medium-sized enterprises, and it is also extremely popular among large enterprises, nearly on par with machine learning for data analysis (Table 1). Identical patterns are observed in EU enterprises, except in the case of text mining, which is used slightly more by large enterprises than machine learning for data analysis. It was to be expected that large enterprises, as the biggest users of AI technologies in general, were also the leading users of each of the listed types of technologies. Besides text mining and machine learning for data analysis, the most popular AI technologies among large enterprises in the EU were AI-based software robotic process automation, speech recognition, and natural language generation, while in Serbia, it was AI-based software robotic process automation. On the other hand, autonomous robots, self-driving vehicles, and autonomous drones, as well as image recognition and image processing, were the least represented in both the EU and Serbia. Similar trends can be observed among small and medium-sized enterprises in both Serbia and the EU regarding the most and least commonly used AI technologies.

Table 1. Enterprises using AI technologies by type of AI technology and size class (% of enterprises), 2024

Type of AI	Serbia			EU		
	Small	Medium	Large	Small	Medium	Large
A	3.25	6.24	7.25	5.76	10.38	21.44
B	1.23	2.14	3.86	4.58	7.88	16.64
C	1.34	3.1	3.56	3.92	7.34	16.7
D	2.44	4.32	7.39	3.13	7.28	20.58
E	1.55	2.8	6.28	3.03	7.62	20.4
F	0.98	1.85	2.78	2.6	4.82	13.4
G	0.03	1	1.8	0.66	1.82	7.19

Note: A - text mining; B - natural language generation; C - speech recognition; D - machine learning (e.g. deep learning) for data analysis; E - AI based software robotic process automation; F - image recognition, image processing; G - autonomous robots, self-driving vehicles, autonomous drones.

Source: Eurostat (2024).

AI technologies found their application in various sectors of economic activity (Table 2). Enterprises in the information and communication sector were the largest users of all types of AI technologies, except for autonomous robots, self-driving vehicles, and autonomous drones in Serbia. The next largest users of almost all types of AI technologies were enterprises engaged in professional, scientific, and technical activities, both in the EU and in Serbia. In Serbia, there were also industries in which certain types of AI technologies were not used at all. Apart from enterprises engaged in real estate activities, which had already been identified as not using AI technologies in their operations (Figure 3), enterprises operating in some other sectors used only specific types of AI technologies. For example, enterprises providing accommodation services used only machine learning for data analysis; enterprises engaged in construction activities did not use machine learning for data analysis, AI-based software robotic process automation, image recognition, image processing, or autonomous robots, self-driving vehicles, and autonomous drones. The last three types of AI technologies were also not used in the sectors of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply; water supply; sewerage, waste management, and remediation activities.

Table 2. Enterprises using AI technologies by type of AI technology and economic activity (% of enterprises), 2024

	Serbia							EU						
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
C	4.63	0.29	0.57	1.2	1	1.18	0.63	4.58	3.53	2.94	2.73	3.23	2.74	1.46
D_E	0.26	0.26	4.46	0.52	0	0	0	5.52	4	4.18	4.75	4.57	3.16	1.13
F	0.55	0.46	0.49	0	0	0	0	2.81	2.42	2.54	0.83	0.95	1.49	0.35
G	0.45	0.56	0.56	3.62	3.23	0.07	0.1	5.98	5.03	3.83	2.96	3.24	2.63	0.8
G47	0.67	1.1	1.22	1.36	0.55	0.22	0.11	5.06	4.52	3.23	2.63	2.79	2.87	0.58
H	0.1	0	8.31	1.1	1.1	1.11	1.01	3.7	3.32	2.83	1.98	2.33	2.4	0.83
I55	0	0	0	0.54	0	0	0	6.91	4.27	3	2.54	2.4	1.47	0.44
J	20.2	15.33	7.38	16.57	6.8	6	0	38.11	25.83	20.13	25.66	21.2	13.54	3.43
L68	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7.2	5.8	6.75	2.93	4.52	2.15	0.45
M	10.16	0.7	0.9	3.82	3.34	2.26	0.23	15.61	11.51	12.49	11.35	10.38	7.35	1.67
N	3.11	0.54	0.46	1.94	0.62	1.81	0	8.06	4.96	4.91	3.96	4.26	2.96	0.69

Note: Explanations of the column symbols can be found in the note below the Table 1. Explanations of the row symbols can be found in the note below Figure 3.

Source: Eurostat (2024).

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Enterprises used AI technologies to perform various tasks (Figure 5). By far, the largest number of enterprises used them for marketing or sales, with the share of enterprises that were using them for this purpose in Serbia being 5.88 percentage points higher than in the EU. The next two most common purposes Serbian enterprises used AI technologies were R&D or innovation activities and production processes, respectively, while in the EU, the ranks of these purposes were reversed. These were followed by accounting, controlling or finance management, and ICT security, with the difference in the share of enterprises using AI for these purposes being relatively small, both in Serbia and the EU. Also, in the EU, the difference between the share of enterprises using AI for these two purposes and for production processes was very small. The fewest enterprises used AI for logistics.

**Figure 5. Enterprises using AI technologies by type of purpose
(% of enterprises using at least one AI technology), 2024**

Source: Eurostat (2024).

Regardless of the size of the enterprise, in Serbia AI technologies were most commonly used for marketing or sales, with small enterprises using them more frequently than medium and large ones (Table 3). The next most common reason for using AI among large and small enterprises was R&D or innovation activities. Nearly the same share of small and large enterprises used AI for this purpose, while the share of medium-sized enterprises was, on average, 12.04 percentage points lower. ICT security was the third most popular purpose among large enterprises, and second among medium-sized enterprises, while no small enterprises were registered as using AI for this purpose. Also, it is striking that a very similar share of small and large enterprises use AI for production processes and accounting, controlling, or finance management, while medium-sized enterprises showed extremely low interest in the latter (less than 1% of users). On the other hand, among large enterprises in the EU, AI was most commonly used for ICT security, followed by production processes and marketing and sales. These purposes were also among the top three for medium-sized enterprises, only in a different order, as well as for small enterprises, except that for them, accounting, controlling, or finance management was among the top three instead of ICT security. The most noticeable

difference compared to enterprises in Serbia is that the use of AI technologies for R&D or innovation activities ranks second to last among all enterprise size classes. There is also a significant discrepancy in the use of AI for ICT security across all enterprise size classes. Lastly, while in Serbia less than 1% of medium-sized enterprises use AI for accounting, controlling, or finance management, in the EU this share is slightly above one-fifth.

**Table 3. Enterprises using AI technologies by type of purpose and size class
(% of enterprises using at least one AI technology), 2024**

Purpose	Serbia			EU		
	Small	Medium	Large	Small	Medium	Large
Marketing or sales	44.84	33.08	30.12	34.9	31.95	33.09
Production processes	11.01	7.22	12.05	21.62	24.76	34.65
Logistics	0.61	4.94	7.23	4.48	7.26	15.85
ICT security	0	19.39	15.66	17.19	28.76	46.44
R&D or innovation	21.1	8.75	20.48	17.41	19.34	25.86
Accounting, controlling or finance management	9.63	0.76	10.84	22.11	22.41	27.4

Source: Eurostat (2024).

In most sectors in Serbia, AI technologies was predominantly used for marketing or sales. For example, all surveyed enterprises in the accommodation sector, slightly more than three fifths in the wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles sector, more than half in the manufacturing sector, and slightly over and close to one third of enterprises in the administrative and support service activities and professional, scientific and technical activities sectors, respectively. Enterprises primarily used AI for production processes in the information and communication sector. For ICT security, AI was mostly used by enterprises in the accommodation and retail trade sectors, excluding the motor vehicles and motorcycles industries. Slightly more than a quarter of enterprises in the manufacturing and administrative and support service activities sectors, and just over a fifth of enterprises in the real estate activities, professional, scientific and technical activities, and information and communication sectors used AI for R&D or innovation activities. AI for accounting, controlling, or finance management was mainly employed in the wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, information and communication, and construction sectors, while AI for logistics was most commonly used in the transportation and storage sector. Moreover, many sectors in Serbia did not utilize AI for specific purposes. For instance, AI technologies for logistics were absent in five sectors, for R&D or innovation, as well as accounting, controlling, or finance management in four sectors, for production processes in three sectors, and for ICT security in one sector. Compared to EU, the share of enterprises using AI for various purposes was significantly lower in most sectors.

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Table 4. Enterprises using AI technologies by type of purpose and economic activity (% of enterprises using at least one AI technology), 2024

	Serbia						EU					
	M/S	PP	L	ICT	RDI	ACF	M/S	PP	L	ICT	RDI	ACF
C	55.75	3.98	3.54	2.21	27.43	3.1	27.11	26.23	9.41	24.27	16.91	20.19
D_E	5	5	0	5	0	0	23.22	26.48	5.22	34.81	16.48	18.68
F	12.5	0	0	12.5	0	12.5	21.35	11.43	2.96	17.94	9.93	22.54
G	77.63	2.63	1.32	9.87	1.32	15.79	45.95	13.16	9.56	19.67	9.6	18.88
G47	13.89	8.33	2.78	38.89	2.78	8.33	52.89	11.47	12.4	13.16	7.38	14.4
H	10.28	0	10.28	0.93	0	0	24.54	18.43	18.78	27.99	9.74	21.68
I55	100	0	0	100	0	0	56.45	14.48	2.82	14.9	4.55	16.64
J	27.24	24.36	0	12.18	22.76	13.14	41.8	36.9	3.78	27.91	43.46	21.32
L68	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	41.16	20.09	3.58	21.08	9.43	26.28
M	31.13	4.64	0.66	0.66	23.18	0.66	23.87	29.1	1.95	19.75	20.48	29.8
N	37.5	16.67	0	0	29.17	0	33.9	20.44	5.68	23.48	11.46	24.95

Note: M/S - marketing or sales. PP - production processes. L - logistics. ICT – ICT security. RDI – Research and development or innovation. ACF - Accounting, controlling or finance management. For row symbols see note below Figure 3. N/A – not available.

Source: Eurostat (2024).

3. Conclusion

The adoption of artificial intelligence technologies among enterprises in Serbia remains limited but is gradually increasing, with large enterprises and the information and communication sector leading the way. While marketing and sales are the most common areas of application, usage across other business functions is still uneven and lags behind EU averages. The findings highlight both the emerging potential and the structural challenges facing Serbian enterprises, pointing to the need for targeted policy support, greater awareness, and strategic investments to accelerate AI integration across sectors and firm sizes.

To fully leverage the benefits of artificial intelligence, Serbia must foster stronger collaboration between industry, government, and research institutions, while addressing gaps in digital skills and infrastructure. Continued monitoring of adoption trends and tailored support for SMEs will be essential in narrowing the gap with EU enterprises and ensuring inclusive, innovation-driven growth.

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UPOTREBA VEŠTAČKE INTELIGENCIJE U PREDUZEĆIMA U SRBIJI

Rezime: Cilj istraživanja je analiza upotebe veštačke inteligencije (AI) u preduzećima u Srbiji. Pored toga, razmotrena je i pozicija u odnosu na preduzeća u Evropskoj uniji. U istraživanju su korišćeni podaci dostupni na Eurostatu. Trenutno, relativno mali broj preduzeća koristi tehnologije veštačke inteligencije, iako se taj broj postepeno povećava. Najveći korisnici su velika preduzeća, dok se među sektorima privredne delatnosti posebno ističe sektor informisanja i komunikacija. Najzastupljenije vrste AI tehnologija koje preduzeća koriste obuhvataju analizu pisanog jezika (rudarenje teksta) i mašinsko učenje (npr. duboko učenje) u svrhu analize podataka. Najveći broj preduzeća primenjuje AI tehnologije u oblasti marketinga i prodaje, kao i u oblasti istraživanja i razvoja i inovacija.

Keywords: Veštačka inteligencija; Mala i srednja preduzeća; Srbija; Evropska unija.